

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. QQ plot for estradiol levels in male individuals. The red line indicates the expected distribution assuming no association.

Supplementary Figure 2. QQ plot for estradiol levels in female individuals. The red line indicates the expected distribution assuming no association

Supplementary Figure 3. One-Sample MR results using effect estimates on estradiol calculated using Tobit modeling. Instrumental Variables are the same as in the main analyses. a) One-sample MR results from females. b) One-sample MR results from males.